

INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF EDUCATION OF THE YOUNG GENERATION

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Abstract. *The article considers innovative pedagogical activity in primary education as a process that is an opportunity for teachers to transfer knowledge, find and develop the germs of creativity, communicate, and for students to constantly “acquire” knowledge based on creativity, the joy of creativity, self-confidence and environment psychological comfort.*

Keywords: *primary education, educational space, innovative activity, educational activity, teacher, student, literacy, student-oriented situations, technologies, tasks, staged creative games and discussions.*

The essence of student-oriented situations in primary education is to interest them in various subjects, to maintain their desire and interest in learning within the framework of educational interaction. In the methodological arsenal of every primary education teacher, there are methods, content and tools to increase the cognitive activity of young students, which serve to successfully involve young school-aged students in the learning process. Of course, these situations, technologies, assignments, there may be staged creative games and discussions.

Here we look at the person-centered situations we use in our training sessions.

Creating a psycho-emotional comfortable environment for students before starting each new educational activity in primary education, that is, thinking about the mood and emotional state in order to establish contact with them. Is recommended. For example, everything on Earth is beautiful. The sky is beautiful, the world is beautiful. Everything about me is great.

You can also start the lesson in another way: - Our greeting today is called "Palm to palm" and we ask by touching our palms to each other. After that, ask the students: What did you feel? Do you feel how hot your hands are? Today's communication with you will be just as warm" - can be seen when setting the educational task with intrigue (arousal of interest).

Performing exercises in Literacy classes of primary education is also a personal situation. For example, the game "Perfect friendship" on the topic "Goodbye to the Uzbek alphabet" is recommended as a literacy lesson for 1st graders. Students are asked to choose a pair for friendship through this game. We read many proverbs and sayings in the alphabet. But do you remember them? Girls are asked to say the beginning of the proverb, and boys are asked to say the end.

It is advisable to use interactive methods in the organization of practical lessons related to phonetics, graphics, orthography, lexicon and morphology in the mother tongue classes of primary education.

Of the state language status to our mother tongue determined the conditions of its vitality and living conditions. Development and prospects are guaranteed by law.

Ensuring that oral speech is fully literary in primary education is related to the standardization of the pronunciation process of students of junior school age. Regardless of the area in which oral speech is used and in what style it is expressed, the issue of applying language

units to one standard is in the first place in all places. Non-observance of orthoepic norms remains one of the serious defects in our speech culture.

Violation of pronunciation standards by the young generation and neglect of their language culture increases illiteracy in society. For this reason, it is our job to try to make young people speak according to Isha speech culture and speech etiquette, and we must ensure that every sound, word, and phrase that is pronounced sounds clear and fluent.

It is not necessary for young people to be eloquent, but it is necessary to express their thoughts and concepts with correct and clear expressions, because it is the honorable duty of every young generation to preserve the purity of our mother tongue.

It should be noted here that primary education Words from foreign dictionaries are widely used in the content of mother tongue and reading literacy textbooks. However, these words cause some difficulties in the pronunciation process of students of junior school age. Because these words are difficult not only for students of small school age, but also for adults [7, 8]. For example, it is natural that the words technology, sensor, virtual, pygmalion in the lesson Mother tongue and reading literacy of the 3rd grade textbook cause spelling errors such as technology, sensor, vertual, pygmalion.

Therefore, in order to convey to the students the unique elegance of our mother tongue, to feel it, to feel it and to use it wisely, in elementary grades in mother tongue classes _ We recommend using the interactive methods of "Kacography" and "Corrector" for the "Rules of Spelling" tasks .

Cocos is derived from the Latin words - bad, ugly, unpleasant and **graphos** - to write " Cacography " method is allowed by the students in the text teaching how to correct certain spelling errors (words that are unpleasant, unpleasant, wrong, and have silly meanings) is used in the target.

So, this method is a collection of dissonant, unpleasant sounds , and the nonsense associated with the writing. orthographic point of view from the didactic point of view, it sheds light on this issue.

Kacography, as one of the interactive methods, helps students to think independently, compare things with each other, search, find a solution to a problem, and most importantly, draw necessary conclusions on certain topics based on the knowledge and skills acquired in the mother tongue classes. Dispels apathy and indifference in students, encourages courage and creativity, eliminates negative characteristics such as muteness, subordination, and inactivity [9, 10]. The cacography method is especially effective in passing practical lessons related to phonetics, graphics, orthography, lexicon and morphology. For example, it is appropriate to use different tasks in "Consolidation Lessons" or "Revision Lessons" after students have been given enough information about vowels and consonants. The main focus is on the difference between spoken and written words.

Our observations show that most of the students do not learn the rules of spelling in their mother tongue classes and get used to writing words as they are pronounced. Dialectal errors in students' speech cause a decrease in their literacy level and misspelling of regular words [11, 12]. For example, words such as price, spring, with, star, theater, question, order, prosperity, pearl, Saturday, responsible, and river are spoken by the students as boho, spring, blan, star, theater, question, Ordin, obot, marvarit, shamba, masul, दौर are pronounced in the form of ordin, and it is common to write mistakes on this basis. This helps them to understand the correct spelling of vowels and consonants and shows that they have sufficient knowledge of the mother tongue. In

order to prevent such mistakes, after providing the students with relevant theoretical information, they are asked to complete the following task: Read the words, find the places where they are written incorrectly, correct them according to the spelling rules, and see them in your notebook. write down. Bugalter, khayal, khayo, holal, mamila, qiqiq, director, conference, computer, maylis, etc. Correct spelling: accountant, imagination, modesty, honest, dealing, honest, law, director, conference, computer, meeting.

Also in the 4th grade Mother tongue class The lesson on the topic " Solving the spelling problem " will be held in the form of a business game "Corrector". Students will imagine that they are in the editorial office and find out that the proofreading task is the responsibility of the editor who is a printing press employee . So, readers will find out in advance who the editor is and what kind of work he does. It is useful to give practical importance to the lessons, instead of twisting and repeating dozens of rules in a traditional and uninteresting way, which makes the lessons of the mother tongue boring and unpleasant.

Also, in the 4th grade, in the mother tongue classes , students can be presented with 3 levels of tasks as a choice proposal.

Students choose their level and complete the task:

Level 1 - find and correct errors;

Level 2 - divide the words into groups:

a) vocabulary words;

b) vowel in root;

c) words with a different spelling;

Step 3 - Write a reply to this girl.

This task allows students to express their subjective opinion. Teacher offers students to choose a method of individual verification of knowledge on a previously studied topic: explanation of terms, description of specific terms; discuss the answers to the questions asked in the microgroup; find synonyms and antonyms of terms completes tasks such as [13, 14].

Recently, it has been noted that children choose test tasks. And this means that they put themselves in a choice situation, because you have to choose one of the 3 answers correctly. Test item used in this lesson. We have come to the following game situations, which are indispensable in primary education.

Organized for the 3rd grade of primary education In the "World around" classes "Journey Around the Planet" It is highly effective to use the "Buy a ticket" business game for students to travel around the world . Because young students by participating in the game They also have an increased interest in science. The systematic introduction of game forms into the educational process really leads to the rapid acquisition of knowledge by most students, which in turn leads to an increase in educational results [15, 16].

Without a sense of achievement, the child loses interest in school and academic activities. The most important aspect in working with students of junior school age is to create a state of success. Because this is the basis for the formation of a positive emotional atmosphere in the classroom. Children should instill confidence in their own strength and capabilities, strive for success. For this, it is appropriate for the teacher to act as a motivator. That is, he says: "You can do it", "You will succeed", "I believe that you can do it" , "I am always with you", "I will always support you", "I will listen to your thoughts, actions" "I support your actions" should be regularly sent to the students . This situation serves to ensure successful situations such as "elimination of

fear", "incentive for a successful result", "introduction of motive", "high evaluation of one's own actions" in students.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in primary education lesson - imparting knowledge for teachers, finding buds of creativity and is an opportunity to develop and communicate. Students and for him - it is the joy of discovery, the "grabbing" of knowledge with constant creativity in an environment of confidence and psychological comfort.

Therefore, in his innovative activities, the primary education teacher should constantly come up with situations that provide an opportunity to show and develop their creative abilities in the education and upbringing of young people.

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